

Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers in Selected Hospitals, Assam

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ABSTRACT

Background: Human milk is the best source of nutrition for all newborn babies. Donor human milk and Breast milk have been shown to be the ideal nutritional option for the most delicate and vulnerable newborns in the neonatal intensive care unit. Human milk donation has a significant role in children's survival when a mother cannot provide her milk for her infant. **Aim:** The objective of the study is to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers in selected hospitals, Assam. **Materials And Methods:** Quantitative research approach with non-experimental descriptive research design was adopted for the study. Sampling technique used in the study was simple random sampling technique with the sample size of 100. The tools used for data collection was demographic variables, structured knowledge questionnaire and 3-point Likert scale for attitude statement regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers. **Results:** The findings of the study shows that antenatal mothers i.e. 52% have inadequate knowledge, 40% have moderately adequate knowledge and 8% have adequate knowledge regarding human milk banking. About 48% of antenatal mothers have moderately favorable attitude, 37% have unfavorable attitude and 15% had favorable attitude towards human milk banking. There was a moderate positive correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking and ($r=0.332$) ($p=0.001$) was significant at $p<0.05$ level of significance. Knowledge was found to be significant associated with demographic variables such as educational qualification, no. of pregnancy and attitude of antenatal mothers was found to have a significant association with educational qualification and type of family. **Conclusion:** Based on the findings, the participants were having inadequate knowledge and moderately favorable attitude. So, it is the responsibility of the health care workers to impart knowledge and encourage the participants to adopt Human Milk Bank (HMB) by providing human milk for premature babies and critically ill babies those are admitted in NICU, for a variety of reasons could not able to access the human milk.

Keywords: Human milk Banking, Breast milk, Knowledge, Attitude, Antenatal mothers

INTRODUCTION

Breast milk is the most important thing for the new born baby as it contains all the primary nutrient required for the newborn baby. Human milk is the best source of nutrition for all newborn babies. More specifically, a mother's breast milk is the first choice of nutrition for those who are preterm, have low birth weight, and are unwell. Donor human milk and Breast milk have been shown to be the ideal nutritional option for the most delicate and vulnerable newborns in the neonatal intensive care unit. The advantages of breast milk to a child are so essential that even the mother's absence must not deprive the baby of them. While a few mothers are urgently attempting to breastfeed their kids despite limited success owing to physical infirmities, surgery, or chronic diseases,

others are unable to give them formula because of the stress, agony, and stomach distress it causes in their babies. The origin of the donation of human milk can be traced to the early days of wet nursing where babies and children were fed by parents, families, and even strangers, in 1980, a joint declaration was issued by the World Health organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) endorsing the use of voluntary donor milk as the first option if the biological mother cannot breastfeed. However, due to the development of the formula milk industry in the world, the use of donor human milk is declining in most of the world. A human milk bank (HMB) is a rigorous service established to recruit breast milk donors, collect donated milk, pasteurize screen, store, and distribute safe donor human milk which is free

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from any physical, chemical, or microbiological contaminants or pathogens to meet infants' specific needs for optimal nutrition and health. The use of expressed human milk for infant feeding, whether through peer-to-peer human milk sharing or commercial markets for human milk and derivative products, is growing globally. Currently, there are more than 500 human milk banks operating in more than 37 countries worldwide, and the number of human milk banks is continuously increasing. However, in Africa, the number of human milk banks established is not more than ten.

Objectives:

1. To assess the level of knowledge regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers.
2. To assess the level of attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers.
3. To find out the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers.
4. To find out the association between knowledge and selected demographic variables regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers.
5. To find out the association between attitude and selected demographic variables regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers.

METHODOLOGY

A non-experimental descriptive study was conducted among 100 women on antenatal mothers in selected hospitals, Assam to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking. The study was conducted in Swahid-Tilak-Hemram-Gunabhiram Civil hospital, Marwari Maternity Hospital, Satribari Christian Hospital, Assam the setting was selected according to researchers convenient. The study was conducted after administrative permission was taken from Dean, Faculty of Nursing, Assam down town University, Guwahati. The ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Committee of Assam down town University, Guwahati. The study was conducted from 14th February to 16th March 2024 on 100 women in antenatal mothers using Simple random sampling technique. The tools used for data collection was demographic variables, structured knowledge questionnaire and 3-point Likert scale for attitude

statement regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers. The data obtained was analyzed in terms of objectives of the study by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Sample Size:

Sample size was decided according to the objectives, resources available, nature of study, method of sampling followed, nature of respondent and nature of population. In this study samples size consists of 100 antenatal mothers that are fulfilling the inclusion criteria. In this study, the Cochran sample size calculation formula was used for calculating the sample size is as follows:

$$n = Z^2 p (1-p) / e^2$$

$$Z = 1.96 \text{ (at 95\% CI)}$$

$$e = 0.05 \text{ (at 95\% CI)}$$

$$p = 0.06\%$$

Where **n** is the sample size, **Z** is the significance level or reliability level (for significance level at 95%) where, **p** is expected population probability and **e** is accepting error ($e=0.05$).

Inclusion criteria:

In this study, the inclusion criteria are antenatal mothers who:

- Gives consent for participation.
- Are available during data collection.
- Are attending Antenatal OPD.
- Can read and understand Hindi, Assamese, and English.

Exclusion criteria:

In this study, the exclusion criteria are antenatal mothers who are:

- In labour pain.

RESULTS

The study was conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers admitted in selected hospitals, Assam.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Selected Demographic Variables of Antenatal Mothers Regarding Human Milk Banking. n = 100

Sl. No.	Demographic Variables	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age in years		
	a) <18 years	61	61%
	b) 19-26 years	21	21%
	c) 27-35 years	10	10%
	d) >35 years	0	0
2.	Religion		
	a. Hinduism	44	44%
	a. Christianity	7	7%
	b. Islam	49	49%
	c. Others	0	0
3.	Educational Qualification		
	a. No formal education	22	22%
	b. Primary	34	34%
	c. Secondary	15	15%
	d. Higher secondary	19	19%
	e. Graduate and above	10	10%
4.	Occupation		
	a. Home maker	79	79%
	b. Private employed	17	17%
	c. Government employed	4	4%
	d. Self employed	0	0
5.	No. of pregnancy		
	a. 1	46	46%
	b. 2	46	46%
	c. 3	7	7%
	d. >4	1	1%
6.	Socio- economic status (income per month)		
	a. 199,862 and above	0	0
	b. 99,931- 199,861	0	0
	c. 74,755- 99,930	0	0
	d. 49,962 – 74,755	0	0
	e. 29,973 – 49,961	4	4%
	f. 10,002 – 29,972	87	87%
	g. Less than 10,001	9	9%
7.	Duration of marriage		
	a. <1 year	23	23%
	b. 1-3 years	73	73%
	c. 4-6 years	4	4%
	d. > 6 years	0	0
8.	Type of family		
	a. Joint family	13	13%
	b. Nuclear family	87	87%
	c. Extended family	0	0
9.	I. Have you ever utilized the services of human milk banking		
	a. Yes	0	0
	b. No	100	100 %
	II. If yes, specify sources....		
10.	I. Any previous information regarding human milk banking		
		9	9%

	a. Yes		
	b. No	91	91%
II. If yes, source of information			
	a. Health care personnel	1	1%
	b. Media	5	5%
	c. Family	3	3%
	d. Friends	0	0

In reference of table-1, the major findings of the studies showed ; were aged characteristics of demographic variables shows that most of the antenatal mothers, 61(61.0%) were aged grouped of <18 years, 49(49.0%) were from Islam religion, 34(34.0%) had no formal education, 79(79.0%) were

housewives, 46(46.0%) already had 2 children, 87(87.0%) had totally family income of 10.002-29.972, 73(73.0%) had 1-3 years of duration of marriage, 87(87.0%) were from joint family, 100(100.0%) had 1never utilized the services of human milk banking.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Knowledge Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers. n=100

Level of knowledge	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Median	Mean	SD
Inadequate (1-6)	52	52	8	9.06	±3.34
Moderately adequate (7-12)	40	40			
Adequate (13-20)	8	8			

In table-2, the study revealed that:

- About 8.0% (8) of the participants had adequate knowledge regarding human milk banking.

- About 40.0% (40) of the participants had moderately adequate knowledge regarding human milk banking.
- 52.0% (52) of the participants have inadequate knowledge regarding human milk banking.

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Attitude Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers. n=100

Level of attitude	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Median	Mean	SD
Unfavorable (1-20)	37	37	23	25.80	±10.13
Moderately favorable (21-40)	48	48			
Favorable (41-60)	15	15			

In table-3, the study revealed that:

- About 37.0% (37) of the participants had unfavourable attitude regarding human milk banking.

- 48.0% (48) of the participants had moderately favourable attitude regarding human milk banking.
- 15.0% (15) of the participants had favourable attitude regarding human milk banking.

Table 4: Correlation Between Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers n=100

Correlation	Mean	SD	r value	p value	Inferences
Knowledge	9.06	±3.34	0.332	0.001*	NS
Attitude	25.80	±10.13			

Note: *p<0.05 level of significance

In table-4, the study shows the mean score of knowledge regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers was 9.34±3.31 and the mean score of attitudes was 25.06±10.14. The calculated Karl Pearson’s Correlation “r” value of r = 0.373 shows a

positive correlation between knowledge and attitude was found to be statistically significant at p<0.001 level. This clearly infers that when knowledge regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers increases their attitude towards it also improves.

Table 5: Association of Level of Knowledge Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers with Selected Demographics n=100

Demographic variables	Knowledge			χ ² value	df	p value
	Inadequate	Moderate	Adequate			
1. Age in years						
a. 18-23 years	29	26	6	7.813	4	0.099 NS
b. 24-28 years	16	13	0			
c. 29-33 years	7	1	2			
d. >35 years	0	0	0			
2. Religion						
a. Hinduism	28	11	5	8.337	4	0.080 NS
b. Christianity	4	3	0			
c. Islam	20	26	3			
d. Others	0	0	0			
3. Educational qualification						
a. No formal education	14	7	1	19.32	8	0.013* S
b. Primary	17	15	2			
c. Secondary	7	7	1			
d. Higher secondary	9	10	0			
e. Graduate and above	5	1	4			
4. Occupation						
a. Home maker	38	35	6	3.547	4	0.471 NS
b. Private employed	11	4	2			
c. Government employed	3	1	0			
d. Self employed	0	0	0			
5. No of pregnancy						
a. 1	28	17	1	27.82	6	0.001* S
b. 2	23	20	3			
c. 3	1	2	4			
a. >4	0	1	0			
6. Income per month						
a. 199,862 and above	0	0	0	1.384	4	0.847 NS
b. 99,931-199,861	0	0	0			
c. 74,755-99,930	0	0	0			
d. 49,962-74,755	0	0	0			
e. 29,973-49,961	2	2	0			
f. 10,002-29,972	45	34	8			
g. Less than 10,001	5	4	0			
7. Duration of marriage						
a. < 1 year	14	7	2	2.344	4	0.673 NS
b. 1-3 years	35	32	6			
c. 4-6 years	3	1	0			
d. > 6 years	0	0	0			

8. Type of family						
a. Joint family	46	33	8	2.010	2	0.366 NS
b. Nuclear family	6	7	0			
c. Extended family	0	0	0			
9. Have you ever utilized the services of human milk banking						
a. Yes	0	0	0	0.042	2	0.979 NS
b. No	52	40	8			
10. Any previous information regarding human milk banking						
a. Yes	4	4	1	0.277	2	0.871 NS
b. No	48	36	7			

*p<0.05 level of significance
significant

NS-Non-

and no. of pregnancy with chi- square value of ($\chi^2=27.82$, $p=0.001$). The other demographic variables did not show statistically significant association with level of knowledge regarding human milk banking with their selected demographic variables.

In table-5, the study shows that the demographic variables educational qualification shown statistically significant association with level of knowledge at $p<0.05$ with chi- square value of ($\chi^2=19.32$, $p=0.013$)

Table 6: Association Of Level Of Attitude Regarding Human Milk Banking Among Antenatal Mothers With Selected Demographics n=100

Demographic variables	Attitude			χ^2 value	df	p value
	Unfavorable	Moderately favorable	Favorable			
1. Age in years				5.393	4	0.249 NS
a. 18-23 years	27	27	7			
b. 24-28 years	7	17	5			
c. 29-33 years	3	4	3			
d. >35 years	0	0	0			
2. Religion				5.067	4	0.280 NS
a. Hinduism	18	18	8			
b. Christianity	1	6	0			
c. Islam	18	24	7			
d. Others	0	0	0			
3. Educational qualification				24.44	8	0.001* S
a. No formal education	7	14	1			
b. Primary	20	11	3			
c. Secondary	6	6	3			
d. Higher secondary	4	12	3			
e. Graduate and above	0	5	5			
4. Occupation				4.020	4	0.403 NS
a. Home maker	32	37	10			
b. Private employed	5	8	4			
c. Government employed	0	3	1			
d. Self employed	0	0	0			
5. No of pregnancy				3.504	6	0.743 NS
b. 1	18	21	7			
c. 2	15	23	8			
d. 3	4	3	0			

e. >4	0	1	0			
6. Income per month						
a. 199,862 and above	0	0	0			
b. 99,931-199,861	0	0	0			
c. 74,755-99,930	0	0	0			
d. 49,962-74,755	0	0	0	4.917	4	0.296 NS
e. 29,973-49,961	0	4	1			
f. 10,002-29,972	34	39	14			
g. Less than 10,001	3	5	0			
7. Duration of marriage						
a. < 1 year	8	8	7	6.351	4	0.174 NS
b. 1-3 years	27	38	8			
c. 4-6 years	2	2	0			
d. > 6 years	0	0	0			
8. Type of family						
a. Joint family	36	40	11	6.517	2	0.038* S
b. Nuclear family	1	8	4			
c. Extended family	0	0	0			
9. Have you ever utilized the services of human milk banking.						
a. Yes	0	0	0	0.029	2	0.985 NS
b. No	37	48	15			
10. Any previous information regarding human milk banking						
a. Yes	2	5	2	1.045	2	0.593 NS
b. No	35	43	13			

***p<0.05 level of significance NS-Non-significant**

In table-6, the study shows that the demographic variable educational qualification shown statistically significant association with level of attitude at p<0.05 with chi- square value of ($\chi^2=24.44$, p=0.001) and type of family with chi- square value of ($\chi^2=6.517$, p=0.038). The other demographic variables did not show statistically significant association with level of attitude regarding human milk banking with their selected demographic variables.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers admitted in selected hospitals, Assam. The study reveals that the demographic variables no. of pregnancy and educational qualification had statistically significant association with level of knowledge regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers. And the demographic variable educational qualification and

type of family had statistically significant association with level of attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers. Findings show a moderate positive correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among antenatal mothers and (p= 0.001) was statistically non-significant at p<0.05 level of significance.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the study findings, the following are made for further study:

- The similar study can be conducted in larger sample for better generalization of the study findings.
- A study to assess the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programmed regarding knowledge and attitude of human milk banking among antenatal mothers in a selected hospital.
- A comparative study to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding human milk banking among

antenatal mothers admitted in Private and Government hospital.

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